

Testing the Associator: Simulating Seismic Events

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V0.3, Documentation for ONC-EEW, June 2018, March - May 2019

1 Overview

The Associator/Correlator module (Rosenberger et al., 2015; Rosenberger et al., 2018) is one of the central pieces of software in the Earthquake Early Warning System (EEWS) under development. Validation of the proposed algorithms and testing their implementation will be one of the main issues in proving and documenting the system. This document attempts to describe the necessary data sets and algorithms to generate realistic simulated event reports as they would be generated by the real-time seismic and seismo-geodetic sites during the dynamic phases of a major earthquake. The final co-seismic displacements however, will *not be part of the simulation* since the associator is so far not making use of those. The simulation would be limited to *point-source* earthquakes, it is not suited to simulate the dynamics of a mega-thrust earthquake. First results are presented in section 7.

2 Input data-sets

2.1 Station data

The current layout of the seismo-geodetic EEW network is shown in figure 1 (as planned, 2017-05-28). The associated table with longitude and latitude data is available as CSV file. This table should be updated over time with actual data from deployed stations.

2.2 Plausible Seismic Epicentres on the Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) and the Explorer Plate

A grid of the so called locked zone of the CSZ including the Explorer Plate was provided by Kelin Wang of NRCan (kelin.wang@canada.ca) and is shown in figure 2. This grid is also available as a CSV file.

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Figure 1: Seismo-geodetic station network as planned in May 2017, the actual final station distribution may deviate.

Figure 2: Three-dimensional grid (red dots), longitude, latitude and depth, covering the assumed locked zone of the CSZ and Explorer plate.

3 Seismic Scaling Relationships

3.1 Period Parameter

The maximum period parameter τ_p as reported from an individual seismometer is distance independent (Wurman, Allen, and Lombard, 2007; Lockman and Allen, 2007; Rosenberger et al., 2015) and depends only on the magnitude M of the event:

$$\tau_p = 10^{\frac{M-c_0}{c_1}} \tag{3.1}$$

with $c_0 = 5.22$ and $c_1 = 6.66$.

Figure 3: τ_p Magnitude scaling relationship after Wurman, Allen, and Lombard, 2007.

3.2 P-wave Displacement Parameter

The scaling relationship for the seismic P-wave displacement parameter, P_d , after Kuyuk and Allen, 2013 is:

$$M = c_0 \log_{10}(P_d^i) + c_1 \log_{10}(R_i) + c_2 \quad (3.2)$$

thus

$$P_d^i(R_i) = 10^{\frac{M - c_1 \log_{10}(R_i) - c_2}{c_0}} \quad (3.3)$$

with $c_0 = 1.23$, $c_1 = 1.38$ and $c_2 = 5.39$.

R_i is the epicentral distance of station i in km , P_d^i is in units of cm .

Figure 4: Seismic-only P_d magnitude scaling relationships for mid-size to large earthquake magnitudes (aft. Kuyuk and Allen, 2013). Assuming a sensitivity in respect to displacements better than $0.1cm$, a $M > 5.0$ earthquake would likely produce a magnitude estimate from stations in less than $10km$ distance, a magnitude $M > 6.0$ would likely trigger reports from stations within about $100km$ distance.

4 Seismo-Geodetic Parameters

The combined seismic acceleration and GNSS Precise Point Positioning (PPP) displacements are processed to yield a high-resolution seismo-geodetic displacement time series, also called "unbiased displacements" (Bock, Melgar, and Crowell, 2011).

4.1 Seismo-geodetic P-wave Displacement

The P-wave displacement P_d vs. magnitude M scaling relationship is given by Crowell et al., 2013 as

$$M = \frac{\log_{10}(P_d^i) + a + c \log_{10}(R_i)}{b} \quad (4.1)$$

with

$$a = 0.893, b = 0.562, c = 1.731$$

thus

$$P_d^i(R_i) = 10^{(bM - c \log_{10}(R_i) - a)} \quad (4.2)$$

P_d is in centimeters and distance R in kilometers.

4.2 Peak Displacements over all Phases of the Seismic Signal

The real-time GNSS equipped sites will also report peak ground displacements, PGD , over the whole duration of an earthquake. PGD is thus also a function of time and typically maximum values coincide with the arrival of the S-phases and possibly later surface wave arrivals.

Crowell et al., 2013 gives the scaling relationship for a site i at distance R_i as:

$$M = \frac{\log(PGD_i) + d}{e - f \log(R_i)} \quad (4.3)$$

with

$$d = 5.013, e = 1.219, f = 0.178$$

then

$$PGD_i(R_i) = 10^{(M(e - f \log_{10}(R_i)) - d)} \quad (4.4)$$

PGD is in centimeters and distance R in kilometers.

For the simulation it is suggested to step the PGD_i value, starting with the P_d^i value (eq. 4.2) 4 seconds after the P-wave arrival, updating it every second while increasing it in a linear fashion to its final value for the assumed magnitude. The maximum value should then be reported at the time of the S-wave arrival.

Figure 5: Seismo-geodetic P_d scaling relationships for mid-size to large earthquake magnitudes (after Crowell et al., 2013). Note, that for an $M_w 5$ earthquake the limits of resolution of the seismo-geodetic system ($\sigma \approx 1\text{cm}$, thick black line) are reached at a hypo-central distance of about 10 km.

Figure 6: Seismo-geodetic PGD magnitude scaling relationships for mid-size to large earthquake magnitudes (aft. Crowell et al., 2013). The limits of resolution for the seismo-geodetic system ($\sigma \approx 1cm$, thick black line) are reached for M_w5 at a hypo-central distance of about 10 km, for M_w6 at about 100 km.

5 General Outline of the Simulation

After picking a grid-point from the data-set shown in figure 2 as the hypocenter and a magnitude, suggested is a range of M4.0 to M8.0, epicentral distances R_i to all stations can be computed. A spherical earth model would be sufficient for the purpose. For deep hypocentres close to individual sites hypocentral distance from a flat earth approximation, $R = \sqrt{R_{epi}^2 + h^2}$, should be used. Initial seismic and seismo-geodetic P_d^i as well as τ_p^i values can be assigned to each instrument site. Ray-tracing would provide the expected P- and S-wave arrivals and the simulation would report the seismic-only P_d^i values four seconds after the theoretical P detection time. Errors should be simulated with random draws from a Gaussian (gamma-) distribution (see for example Press et al., 1992, chapter 7, Octave/Matlab function *random*. Something similar should be available in the Python *numpy* library) with standard deviation of 15% of the computed P_d^i value. The same applies to the distant independent τ_p^i values, error modelling should vary input magnitude on a per-station basis with a standard deviation of 0.7 magnitude units, also drawn from a Gaussian distribution.

With a final seismic $P_d^i < 0.001cm$ a site should be considered as "not triggered" and taken out of the subsequent simulations.

The simulation of seismo-geodetic P_d and PGD is more involved since three solutions from different corrections, broadcast orbits (BO), floating point ambiguity (FA) and integer ambiguity (IA) resolution are required together with their respective standard deviations. Suggested are standard deviations of

$$\sigma_{BO} = 5.0cm$$

$$\sigma_{FA} = 2.0cm$$

$$\sigma_{IA} = 1.0cm$$

and again random errors, drawn from a Gaussian distribution with the respective σ , should be added to the P_d^i and PGD^i value. As indicated earlier, PGD^i for each station is reported in one second time intervals after the P-wave arrival time with linear increments, starting with the P_d^i value and approaching the computed PGD^i value coincident with the S-wave arrival time.

For a realistic scenario, random drop-outs of one or more of the BO, FA or IA based seismo-geodetic values P_d and PGD can be part of a possible simulation to test the recovery of the associator algorithms.

6 Limitations

Capping the magnitude range at a maximum magnitude of M8.0 seems arbitrary but the proposed simulation method can only simulate point-source earthquakes and would not be able to realistically simulate a mega-thrust event.

7 First Results

We tested the capability of the Associator to estimate the correct epicentre of an event and calculated P-wave travel-times to stations in the array for a regular $0.3 \text{ deg} \times 0.3 \text{ deg}$ grid of potential earthquake locations with a standard ray-tracing package. All simulated events have a hypo-central depth of 20 km . We then used only the first four, six and ten arrivals for association to simulate the progression of time as more and more stations detect the event. The condition number for the matrix inversion of the Linearized Least Squares (LLS) algorithm serves as a first proxy for the quality of a solution, an example is shown in figure 7. This was confirmed in another simulation where the P-wave detection times were contaminated with random errors of varying magnitudes. High condition numbers amplify errors in the input data and affect epicentre locations as well as magnitude estimates since those depend on epicentral distances.

The distance between the true epicentre and the solution computed with both, the Direct Grid Search and the LLS algorithm is shown in figure 8 after the first ten P-wave arrivals have been detected.

To test the sensitivity of the associator to timing errors in the P-wave detection times we determined P-wave arrival times by ray-tracing as in the previous simulation but perturbed those with draws from a zero mean, Gaussian distribution with different standard deviatons, σ . The result is shown in figure 9.

Figure 7: The Linearized Least Squares algorithm's condition number is a proxy for the reliability of the epicentre location. Here the first six stations have detected an event located anywhere in the geographic region. Grey areas mark the regions where no solution could be obtained. Condition numbers > 30 are connected predominately to regions where the relative base-line of the respective six station array is short. Red triangles mark the location of currently active seismic stations.

Figure 8: The distribution of errors in epicentre locations from the combined algorithms after the first ten stations have detected the P-wave arrival. The scale is labelled in meters. The dark red regions mark errors of 10km and greater. The larger errors in the north-west, south-east and south-west areas are due to the fact that the station array consisting of the first ten stations has a relatively short base lengths in the direction of sources in that area and consequently has limited range resolution.

Figure 9: The distribution of errors in epicentre locations from the combined algorithms after the first ten stations have detected the P-wave arrival. The P-wave arrival times were perturbed with random errors from a zero mean Gaussian distribution with standard deviation of $\sigma = 5.0s$. The scale here is labelled in kilometers. As expected, the overall pattern does not display a purely random distribution of epicentral errors but rather matches that of figure 7 since the condition number is a proxy describing how errors in the input data affect errors in the final result. The result also confirms that the initial direct grid search with its "spatial histogram" approach (Moni and Rickard, 2009) is well suited to adapt to errors in the time differences of arrival, only epicentres in the grey areas close to the map's boundary would not produce any result.

References

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